

Spin-Valley Polarization Control in WSe₂ Monolayers using Photochemical Doping

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The influence of a photochemical doping method on the spin-valley polarization degree (P_c) of excitons in WSe₂ monolayers is reported. By varying the carrier density and transitioning from an excess of electrons (n-type) to an excess of holes (p-type), a non-monotonic dependence of P_c on the doping level is observed. Using controlled, single-shot photochlorination steps, this non-monotonic behavior is unveiled, with P_c reaching a minimum value of less than 10% at 78 K near the charge neutrality point, while increasing by a factor of three at a hole density of $5 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The impact of the doping on P_c is explained using a phenomenological model that accounts for various mechanisms influencing exciton polarization dynamics, including exciton-carrier scattering processes and exciton-to-trion conversion rates. Among these, exciton-carrier collisions emerge as the dominant mechanism driving the observed variations in P_c , while the exciton effective lifetime remains nearly independent of doping. These findings highlight the potential of photochemical methods for investigating valley physics and for effectively tuning the exciton polarization degree in transition metal dichalcogenide monolayers.

1. Introduction

In monolayer transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs), the local extrema of electronic bands in momentum space at the K^+ and K^- points of the Brillouin zone are associated with a quantum number of ten termed “valley pseudospin”. This degree of freedom has attracted significant interest due to its potential to serve as an additional information carrier, complementing the electron’s charge and spin and offering opportunities for encoding, processing, and storing information in emerging valleytronic applications.^[1] This concept mirrors spintronics, where the spin of electrons and their associated magnetic moment introduce an additional intrinsic degree of freedom.^[2] The manipulation of valleys is a well-established concept, historically involving inversion layers

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at silicon/insulator interfaces,^[3] as well as strain^[4] and magnetic fields in 2D electron-gas systems.^[5] The primary aim of valleytronics is to develop systems that can provide clear advantages in terms of processing speed, energy efficiency, and information storage, thereby complementing and surpassing contemporary semiconductor technologies based on charge and spin.

The origin of the “valley pseudospin” in TMDs lies primarily in the symmetry of electronic states near the *K*-points, complying with time inversion but requiring a broken inversion symmetry, a condition met in odd-numbered TMD layers.^[6] Specifically, monolayers of TMDs exhibit a direct bandgap at the *K*⁺ and *K*⁻ points of the Brillouin zone, where chiral optical selection rules apply. These valleys can be selectively populated by circularly polarized light with opposite helicity, enabling the optical generation and detection of valley polarization (as the spin and valley degrees of freedom are locked, we will use in the following the single term “valley”).^[7] This phenomenon has been explored not only in linear spectroscopy experiments,^[8,9] but also in nonlinear studies.^[10–13] Importantly, the optical response of TMD monolayers is primarily governed by excitons, *i.e.*, Coulomb-bound electron-hole pairs.^[14] Photoluminescence (PL) experiments serve as a convenient tool to study the valley degree of freedom, where for one-photon transitions the exciton-photon coupling is determined by the symmetry of the excitonic wave functions.^[15] Upon circular excitation, the imbalance between right (σ^+) and left (σ^-) circularly polarized exciton emission intensity is measured to extract the valley polarization degree, P_c . The steady state of P_c is determined by the effective lifetime, τ_r , and the valley polarization lifetime, τ_v , through the equation^[14]:

$$P_c = \frac{P_0}{1 + \frac{\tau_r}{\tau_v}} \quad (1)$$

where P_0 is the initially generated polarization that reaches unity for close-to-resonance conditions in accordance with the selection rules.^[16] Equation (1) indicates that P_c is significantly influenced by the interplay between τ_r and τ_v . In particular, a high P_c typically requires a long polarization lifetime as compared to the effective lifetime: $\tau_r \ll \tau_v$.

Engineering the P_c and understanding valley relaxation processes in TMDs pose significant challenges, yet they are pivotal for unlocking the potential of valleytronic applications. The P_c in TMD monolayers is conventionally measured under cryogenic temperatures (4 K), magnetic fields, and resonant excitation. Its value is influenced by various factors, including energy detuning,^[17–21] temperature,^[22–24] and strain,^[25–28] to name a few examples. Interestingly, while electrostatic doping has recently emerged as an effective approach for modulating valley polarization in gated monolayers —particularly in the n-type regime^[29–32]— studies addressing the p-type doping regime remain comparatively scarce, leaving the influence of finite hole density on the P_c less explored.

In this work, we overcome the complexities of gated sample fabrication by introducing a straightforward photochemical method to engineer the exciton’s circular polarization degree in 1L-WSe₂ monolayers. This approach uses single-pulse variation of the carrier density to transition from the n-type to the p-type

regime, all without the need for an applied gate voltage.^[33] This method is versatile and can be applied to 1L-WSe₂ on arbitrary substrates, offering a significant advantage in terms of simplicity and adaptability. The monolayer doping induced by the photochemical method is first evidenced by the change of the PL spectra exhibiting the recombination of charged excitons. We achieve a threefold modulation of the exciton polarization degree under non-resonant excitation conditions, further underscoring the effectiveness and robustness of our approach. To support and explain our findings we present a model, concluding that exciton-carrier collisions constitute the most dominant mechanism driving the observed variations in P_c .

2. Experimental Section

The primary focus of this investigation was a 1L-WSe₂ on hexagonal boron nitride flakes (hBN) deposited on SiO₂/Si substrates (SiO₂ was 285 nm-thick). The monolayers were obtained through mechanical exfoliation from a bulk crystal (2D semiconductors) using a Nitto Denko tape (see more details in Section SI of Supporting Information). A schematic representation, illustrating the side view of the heterostructure, is displayed in **Figure 1a**. To improve the optical quality of the monolayers, thick (≈ 100 nm) hBN flakes were used as supporting substrates.^[35–38] Additionally, detailed information and experimental data concerning reference samples 1L-WSe₂ transferred directly to SiO₂/Si are available in the Supporting Information. However, the spectral broadening caused by disorder at the SiO₂ interface prevents an accurate determination of the peak positions and the intrinsic linewidths. For this reason, the analysis of samples transferred onto hBN for superior optical quality was selected throughout the main text.

For polarization measurements, the sample was excited with circularly polarized light with a photon energy of 1.95 eV (635 nm). Right-handed circularly polarized light (σ^+) was focused on 1L-WSe₂ in a μ -PL (micro-photoluminescence) experimental setup with a combination of a liquid crystal variable retarder (LCVR) and a linear polarizer in the detection path. The emitted PL signal was converted by the LCVR from σ^+ (positive helicity) and σ^- (negative helicity) into the linear basis, and the linear polarizer analyzed the two orthogonal PL components (I_+ and I_-). The degree of spin-valley polarization is given by

$$P_c = \frac{I_+ - I_-}{I_+ + I_-} \quad (2)$$

where I_+ (I_-) represents the intensity of the σ^+ (σ^-) components,^[7,8] associated with the population imbalance of excited carriers within one of the two inequivalent *K* valleys.

The photochlorination process involved the irradiation of 1L-WSe₂ using a pulsed KrF excimer UV laser at 248 nm, directed through a set of mirrors. The pulse duration was 20 ns, the repetition rate was 1 Hz, and the laser beam fluence was 10 mJcm⁻². The monolayer was positioned inside a vacuum chamber, first pumped down to 10 Torr and subsequently exposed to Cl₂ gas with a pressure of 120 Torr. Each photochlorination step involved exposing the monolayer to a single UV pulse in the presence of Cl₂, followed by characterization using optical spectroscopy. This process was repeated, with the accumulated laser pulses

Figure 1. a) Schematic illustration of the side view of the sample irradiated by a KrF (248 nm, UV) excimer laser. The metal atoms (W) are represented by magenta spheres, the chalcogen atoms (Se) by yellow spheres, and the Cl atoms by red spheres. The hBN flake is shown in blue, and the SiO₂ substrate is depicted in grey. The pulse duration is 20 ns and the repetition rate 1 Hz. b) PL spectra of 1L-WSe₂/hBN at 78 K with an excitation wavelength of 635 nm for different numbers of UV laser pulses (LP). The corresponding circular polarization is also displayed (red scatter).

(LP) changing the carrier density in the material due to adsorption of Cl₂ species on the 1L-WSe₂ chalcogen vacancy sites. The entire method was carried out at room temperature; for more information on the adsorption mechanism, see Refs. [33, 39]. An optical microscopy image along with the corresponding Raman spectrum of the sample is shown in Sections SI and SIII (Supporting Information). The monolayer thickness was verified by Raman spectroscopy with a prominent peak observed at approximately 250 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the two degenerate first-order Raman modes E' and A₁' of 1L-WSe₂ along with their 11 cm⁻¹ difference from the second order 2LA(M) mode.^[40–42] Raman analysis also confirmed that the 1L-WSe₂ lattice remains structurally intact throughout the photochlorination process. The degenerate E' / A₁' vibrational mode of monolayer 1L-WSe₂ showed negligible variations in peak position, full width at half maximum (FWHM), and intensity across all doping steps—well within the experimental uncertainty. These observations indicated that no measurable strain, lattice disorder, or material degradation was introduced during photochlorination (see Sections SII, Supporting Information).

3. Results

In Figure 1b, PL spectra of 1L-WSe₂ for the pristine monolayer (LP = 0), as well as two indicative photochlorination steps (LP = 1 and LP = 7) are presented. The circular polarization of the complete PL spectral range is also demonstrated with red points,

extracted by Equation (2). In the pristine sample (LP = 0), the PL spectrum is predominantly characterized by X⁰ at 1.712 eV and a lower energy peak at 1.683 eV. The latter is attributed to negatively charged trions, X⁻ (the sample is naturally electron-doped) due to its characteristic energy difference (ΔE) from X⁰ of approximately 30 meV.^[43,44] Other emission channels, including those involving localized states and phonon replicas, result in a broad feature (L) near 1.6 eV. Following the initial irradiation step (LP = 1), a reduction of X⁻ intensity is observed, accompanied by a noticeable redshift of X⁰ compared to its initial energy position. This observation is in agreement with a strong reduction of the residual electron density of the pristine sample due to the partial passivation of defect sites via adsorption of Cl₂ molecules.^[33] Upon increasing the laser pulses to LP = 7, a new peak emerges ≈ 20 meV below X⁰, attributed to positively charged trions X⁺.^[45] Notably, the circular polarization degree at the energy of X⁰ exhibits a significant enhancement at LP = 7, reaching $\approx 25\%$, compared to just $\approx 9\%$ at LP = 1. We note that neutral biexcitons (DX⁰) also lie close to X⁰ with a binding energy of 15 meV.^[43] However, the contribution from DX⁰ in our optical spectra is excluded by observing a linear power dependence using the same excitation wavelength (see Section SIII, Supporting Information).^[46–49]

The intensity of X⁺ raises with the number of irradiation laser pulses, from LP = 3 to LP = 7, reflecting an increase in the hole density of the material. This effect saturates after LP = 7, likely due to the complete passivation of defect sites through

Figure 2. Carrier density calibration of the photochlorination process in the p-type regime. a) Comparison of the PL intensity ratio of X⁰ to X⁺ as a function of hole density between gated (dashed line)^[34] and photochlorinated (green triangles) 1L-WSe₂. Three green triangles correspond to different laser pulses, LP = 3, LP = 5 and LP = 7. b) Energy difference between X⁰ and X⁺ as a function of the hole density for electrostatically gated (dashed line) and photochlorinated (green triangles) monolayer WSe₂.

Cl₂ adsorption. A similar behavior is observed in the reference 1L-WSe₂/SiO₂/Si sample, as shown in Section SIV (Supporting Information). Determining the precise hole density for the irradiation steps where X⁺ appears is crucial for understanding the exciton polarization, as discussed later. A reliable way to convert the photochlorination pulses into carrier density is to compare the optical response between the photochlorinated 1L-WSe₂ and a calibrated, electrostatically gated 1L-WSe₂.^[34] We employ two approaches to estimate the hole density after LP = 3, LP = 5 and LP = 7: one is based on the intensity ratio (Figure 2a) and the other one on the energy difference (Figure 2b) between X⁰ and X⁺ in the p-type regime. A comparison of the X⁰/X⁺ PL intensity ratio for the electrostatically gated 1L-WSe₂ (black dashed line in Figure 2a) and the photochlorinated sample (green triangles in Figure 2a) indicates an increase in hole density from approximately 4 × 10¹¹ cm⁻² to 5 × 10¹¹ cm⁻² as the irradiation progresses from LP = 3 to LP = 7.^[34] Using a similar approach, the residual electron density of the pristine sample (LP = 0) is estimated to be 1.5 × 10¹¹ cm⁻², with the sample approaching the

carrier neutrality point after a single irradiation pulse (LP = 1), not shown in Figure 2a. The energy difference (ΔE) between X⁰ and X⁺ is also sensitive to the hole density due to the renormalization of the exciton and trion energies, as well as the band gap and binding energy of excitons and trions in the presence of a Fermi sea of holes (Figure 2b).^[50] Based on ΔE, the estimated hole density ranges from approximately 2.5 × 10¹¹ cm⁻² to 5 × 10¹¹ cm⁻² when comparing the electrostatically gated 1L-WSe₂ (dashed line) to the photochlorinated sample (green triangles), see Figure 2b. The small divergence at LP = 3 between Figure 2a,b is attributed to the inhomogeneous broadening of the sample, which affects the fitting process used to determine the precise positions and intensities of X⁰ and X⁺. To statistically estimate the carrier density at different photochlorination steps, both methods (intensity ratio and energy difference) are averaged, with the standard deviation included in Figure 3. Overall, we conclude that as the photochlorination progresses from LP = 0 to LP = 7, the carrier density of 1L-WSe₂ transitions from 1.5 × 10¹¹ cm⁻² electrons (n-type) to 5 × 10¹¹ cm⁻² holes (p-type). Note that PL measurements at

Figure 3. a) Circular polarization of X⁰ as a function of carrier density at 78 K, with circularly polarized laser excitation of 635 nm. LP indicates the number of UV photochlorination pulses. b) FWHM of X⁰ as a function of carrier density at 78 K. The error bars are extracted by analyzing the variation of the reduced chi-square (χ^2) as a function of the fitted neutral exciton FWHM. The uncertainty range is defined by identifying the FWHM values at which χ^2 increases by 10%, along with the standard deviation from different sample locations. The black dashed lines in (a) and (b) represent model calculations. c) Root mean square of the longitudinal-transverse splitting for different carrier densities. Pink dashed line corresponds to the average value.

various sample areas (see Section SV, Supporting Information) confirm that photochlorination yields a homogeneous doping profile, with variations comparable to those typically observed in electrostatically gated TMD samples.

We now analyze the influence of carrier density on the PL circular polarization degree, P_c , of X^0 . Figure 3a presents the variation of P_c across different photochlorination steps, ranging from LP = 0 to LP = 7. For the analysis presented in Figure 3a, P_c of X^0 is extracted by fitting the PL spectra with Lorentzian functions. This approach allows us to isolate the contribution of X^0 from overlapping spectral features, such as X^T , thus ensuring a more accurate estimation of P_c . A non-monotonic behavior is observed: P_c starts at 18% when the sample is doped with $1.5 \times 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$ electrons, decreases to 9% near the neutrality point, and then gradually rises to 25% at $5 \times 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$ holes. This remarkable modulation of ≈ 3 highlights the significant impact of carrier density on the spin-valley relaxation of excitons in the material. To gain further insight into the interaction between excitons and carriers, we examine various factors that may influence exciton relaxation processes.

We recall that the main mechanism of the valley relaxation of bright excitons in TMD monolayers is related to the long-range exchange interaction between electron and hole in the exciton.^[51–53] The exchange interaction produces a longitudinal-transverse splitting of excitons $\hbar\Omega_{\text{LT}}$ and acts as an effective magnetic field that causes exciton pseudospin precession while the scattering processes randomize the precession and result in the valley polarization decay with the rate^[15,51,54]

$$\frac{1}{\tau_v} = \langle \Omega_{\text{LT}}^2 \tau_{\text{sc}} \rangle \quad (3)$$

where τ_{sc} is the scattering time, $\Omega_{\text{LT}}\tau_{\text{sc}} \ll 1$ is assumed, and angular brackets denote the ensemble average. The doping, generally, affects both Ω_{LT} and τ_{sc} in Equation (3). Screening of the long-range exchange interaction in the presence of carriers (i.e., reduction of Ω_{LT}) has been proposed as the main mechanism to prolong the valley relaxation time.^[31,32,55] However, the carrier's Fermi energy given by (under an assumption of population only in the bottom spin subband in each valley):

$$E_F = \frac{\pi \hbar^2 n}{m^*} \quad (4)$$

where n is the carrier density and m^* the effective mass, varies from ≈ 0.6 meV for $1.5 \times 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$ electrons to ≈ 3 meV for $5 \times 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$ holes in the present work. For the exchange interaction, the screening should be taken at the frequency $\omega \approx \omega_0$, where ω_0 is the exciton resonance frequency (in 1L-WSe₂, $\hbar\omega_0 \approx 1.7$ eV).^[56,57] Consequently, $\hbar\omega_0$ exceeds by far the carrier's E_F for the samples studied here and, hence, at such high frequencies the resident carriers are unable to react to the rapidly varying fields created by the electron-hole interaction making screening inefficient.^[57]

The exciton-to-trion conversion can influence the relaxation dynamics of excitons, leading to a shorter effective lifetime, τ_r , of X^0 resulting in higher P_c .^[29] The estimates of the trion forma-

tion rate presented in Ref. [58] show that variation of τ_r in a given density range is negligible. These estimates are further supported by experimental studies of trion dynamics at doping densities similar to those explored here, revealing a trion PL rise time on the picosecond scale.^[59] At the same time, we observe significant variation of the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of X^0 on carrier density. Figure 3b shows that the FWHM(X^0) decreases by approximately 1 meV when transitioning from the electron-rich regime to near the neutrality point, and then increases by about 10 meV as the hole density reaches $5 \times 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$ which cannot be ascribed to the trion formation process. To investigate whether τ_r contributes to the observed variations in the FWHM, time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) measurements were performed using an excitation wavelength of 633 nm to compare the effective lifetime of X^0 in intrinsic (LP = 1) and p-doped (LP = 7) 1L-WSe₂ samples (Section SVI, Supporting Information). For both samples, τ_r is found to be similar, with a value of approximately 1 ps at 80 K, primarily governed by non-radiative decay channels. These results are consistent across various positions on the samples.

Hence, we conclude that i) the variation of P_c with doping is unrelated to τ_r , and, ii) the FWHM is controlled by the scattering processes with $\text{FWHM} = \hbar/\tau_{\text{sc}}$. Indeed, exciton-carrier scattering is known to be an important homogeneous broadening channel both in classical two-dimensional systems based on quantum wells^[60] and TMD monolayers.^[61,62] According to Equation (3) a reduction of τ_{sc} with doping slows down exciton valley relaxation resulting in an increase of P_c observed in experiments. Analytical model of Ref. [62] results in

$$\frac{\hbar}{\tau_{\text{sc}}} = \delta + E_T \frac{M_T}{M_X} \frac{\pi}{\ln^2\left(\frac{\delta}{2E_T}\right) + \frac{\pi^2}{4}} \quad (5)$$

where δ is the homogeneous contribution to FWHM related to other scattering processes, such as exciton-phonon scattering, M_T and M_X are the trion and exciton translational masses and E_T is the trion binding energy. Equation (5) is derived for the degenerate electrons, for non-degenerate charge carriers it is different by a logarithmic factor. Dashed line in Figure 3b shows the FWHM calculated after Equation (5) in reasonable agreement with the experiment. Some discrepancy with the data results from simplification of the analytical model and possible additional factors that affect FWHM such as local disorder. Using root mean square of the longitudinal-transverse splitting as a fitting parameter and taking $\tau_r = 1$ ps, $P_0 = 100\%$ we obtain the black dashed curve in Figure 3a for $\langle (\hbar\Omega_{\text{LT}})^2 \rangle^{1/2} = 8$ meV which is in agreement with the experiment. Importantly, we can confirm this value without using any particular theoretical model for the scattering time: Indeed, taking into account the smallness of P_c and combining Equations (1) and (3), we obtain $\langle (\hbar\Omega_{\text{LT}})^2 \rangle = (\hbar\text{FWHM})/(\tau_r P_c)$. Using experimental values of the FWHM for all available densities we get $\langle (\hbar\Omega_{\text{LT}})^2 \rangle^{1/2}$ in the range 7 to 11 meV, see Figure 3c.

We note that the transfer of exciton polarization to resident carriers or transitions from spin-bright to spin-dark states are less important mechanisms in the observed modulation of P_c .

In Figure 4, we present the temperature-dependent behavior of circular polarization for specific carrier densities. The

Figure 4. Circular polarization of neutral excitons as a function of temperature for different carrier densities, using a 635 nm excitation wavelength. Experimental values are presented by spheres while the model is shown with dotted curves.

corresponding helicity-resolved PL spectra can be found in Section SVII (Supporting Information). Similarly to the analysis presented in Figure 4, P_c of X^0 in Figure 4 is also extracted from a full fit of the PL spectra. Stronger variations in the exciton's polarization are observed at low temperatures. As expected, there is a notable decrease in polarization with increasing temperature for each doping level condition of the system. Regardless of doping level, at room temperature ($T = 300$ K), the degree of polarization significantly diminishes, nearly approaching zero. It is consistent with the valley depolarization driven by the electron-hole exchange interaction: Ω_{TH} scales approximately linearly with the wavevector k of exciton resulting in $\tau_v \propto 1/T$.^[63] Hence, P_c decreases as T^{-1} at the temperature-independent scattering time τ_{sc} as shown by corresponding dotted curves in Figure 4 calculated using $\langle (\hbar\Omega_{\text{TH}})^2 \rangle^{1/2} = 8$ meV at $T = 78$ K and temperature-independent τ_{sc} determined from the FWHM at the same temperature. Note that while our model based on long-range exchange-driven valley depolarization captures the general trend of the circular polarization degree P_c , it underestimates its rapid quenching at temperatures above 150 K. To further investigate this discrepancy, we analyze the exciton linewidth broadening from temperature-dependent PL spectra across different doping levels (see Section SVIII, Supporting Information). The extracted broadening, $\Gamma(T)$, is fitted using a model that includes both acoustic and optical phonon scattering contributions, and the resulting $\Gamma(T)$ is used to adjust the calculation of the valley relaxation time τ_v , following the Dyakonov–Perel mechanism. Despite this revision, the calculated $P_c(T)$ exhibits a saturation at high temperatures, in contrast to the experimentally observed decrease. This calculated behavior can be understood as follows: $\Gamma(T)$ increases approximately

linearly with temperature, effectively compensating the linear increase of Ω_{TH}^2 with temperature. Observed deviations suggest that additional mechanisms not captured by the exchange-only model must be considered. In particular, increasing energy detuning between the fixed excitation energy and the redshifted exciton emission at elevated temperatures likely enhances the loss of valley polarization during exciton thermalization. Such effects, which reduce the initial polarization P_0 , are not explicitly included in our current framework. Additionally, the possible non-linearity of the $\Omega_{\text{TH}}(k)$ dependence—related, for example, to the dielectric contrast in the structure^[64]—the temperature dependence of exciton lifetimes, governed by both radiative and non-radiative decay channels, and the possible thermal activation of dark excitons, may also play roles in the enhanced depolarization.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, our study demonstrates a strong—by a factor of *three*—modulation of the circular polarization degree in neutral exciton emission in 1L- WSe_2/hBN through a photo-induced chemical doping process. We observe that the circular polarization of X^0 increases with carrier density in both n-type and p-type regimes. Between different mechanisms that impact the circular polarization degree, we conclude that exciton-carrier collisions primarily influence the exciton's spin relaxation time (τ_v), while the radiative lifetime (τ_r) remains practically unchanged. These findings highlight the potential of photochemical doping as a useful method for tailoring and fine-tuning the valleytronic properties of 2D materials, with promising applications in optoelectronics and nanophotonics.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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